

Difficulties Faced By Marathi Medium Students to Learn English Language & Their Attitude towards it.

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Abstract

International language English make little important to development of rural areas in comparing to metro cities in India. How population migrated from village to city for getting better life and financial development. Those whose having proficiency in English language help this migrant to get job and good opportunities in cities and specially in Europe and USA countries. English education system introducing India in 1980s. English language don't use in rural areas as compared to urban areas but nowadays there is a need to speak and learn English to villagers also if they want to go with the global world and they have Support of technology to improve it but till there are differences in the proficiency in English in rural and urban area students. this paper is giving to a interpretations on English language teaching and learning environment in rural area of Maharashtra Raigad district it will focus on learning and teaching problems of English language.

Introduction

Language play the important role to development of the human because it is a medium of communication. English is a global language it helps to more impactful in development of a person across the world. English education was introduced by British while they were ruling on India. The high class of Indian society can afford the English medium education but tribes, farmers, low class and medium class society couldn't afford English education in Present period. English become a popular and a key of development of India cities but tribal and rural society untouched by the development which bring by the English. In school teaching English object tools is to developed communication ability among these students but we observe huge differences in English learning in rural areas and in the urban areas. In urban areas students are good in English communication but in rural areas students are struggling to learn English and they develop the phobia of English they start to keep away themselves from English speakers and they struggle to learn English properly. This paper will present the interpretations of English language environment and teaching English in rural areas of Maharashtra and will point out the problems and the difficulties to learn the English as a global language by the rural students.

Teaching English in school and colleges

School play vital role in development of education in society students and institutions have to be proactive to acquiring skills through curriculum and academic environment to a successful education system school scenario of English language is most crucial stage in education and give great impact to developed basic language skills listening, speaking, reading and writing We have unified education system in Maharashtra board in Maharashtra regional language is Marathi all used to speak in

Marathi. English language use limited in rural area Raigad district I have observe more students speak Marathi but in metropolitan's cities for example Mumbai centers colleges medium of instruction in English but what I have observed in ruler Raigad district mostly medium of instruction it's Marathi because if teacher gives the instruction in English students don't understand the topic which is though by the teacher in the classroom.

So teacher had to use translation method to teach the rural students so student understands the topic easily and all subjects teaching and evaluation done through only regional language and only Hindi teach in Hindi and English teaches in English so overall students are in only Marathi language environment but when they enter into the college at that time they start to face difficulties because mostly college is medium of instruction in English so students started to bunk the lectures. so that mostly teacher have to teach in Marathi to make students understand the topic of any subject we have two option to write exam paper at UG level one is original language and another one is the English language so in rural areas students mostly select to regional language to the medium's they also lost their chance to learn English language over there also.

Difficulties in ELT

There are differences among teaching to rural and urban area students by using English language Some features are in English language learning and proficiency among urban and rural students these are follows.

1. Resources of education:

Urban student can access better resources so that they have better chance to develop language .But rural area students don't have enough resources due to The low economic background and it's affect to learn international

language which is required to their development in present global world.

2. **Background of family:** Family background played the key role in developing a performance of child in education and to learn English. rural families mostly ignore educational needs of their child as it's affecting the performance of students in education. mostly rural families are monolingual and it makes them to face difficulties to learn English.

3. **ELT facilities in classroom:** English learning clinic, English language laboratory facilities increases The exposure of English and developed skills of languages but in rural Area students don't get this facility available in there school and colleges.

4. **Trained and qualified teachers:** There are qualified teachers in rural areas colleges and school but the Marathi environment of rural areas colleges creates phobia of English among these students and students fixed in mind that English is very difficult language and they start to stay away from English subject English teachers they start to bunk English lecture because they don't understand the topic taught in classroom which talked in English language and to make student attend to in English lectures English teacher have to speak Marathi with the students they have to use translation method and it's become difficult task to English teacher to teach English in Marathi they have to spend lots of energy to make student understand the topic to make them comfortable in English lecture. Teacher have well qualified but only English teacher can't create an atmosphere of English in college or in school there is a need to create English atmosphere in college by teaching all subject in English then and then students will become familiar with this language and it will help to reduce their phobia of English which will going to develop their career.

5. **Write attitude and motivation for language learning:**

Write attitude and motivation for language learning because positively and negatively it's a affect learning there is a need for proper guidance and active participation of students to learn English language. in rural area student want to practice to speak in English but other student make a fun of that's students who is trying to speak in English this kind of environment develop fearness about English so environment should be motivational if a student wants to practice then college teacher and classmates have to motivate theme.

6. **Classroom size:**

Rural arias classroom size is more than 60 in school and 120 in college per classroom which not allow a teacher to pay equal attention to each students and its gate of affect that students not able to gate prior attention of a teacher. Rather than that teacher has lots of other documentational work as well as so it makes teachers so busy which also affect to divert teachers attention and energy.

7. **Mindset is exanimated :**

Curriculum of college mostly talk as exam point of view by students mostly and its shifts their focus from language learning towards mostly passing in the exam. so educational quality does not fulfill the main object of learning English.

8. **Practice of pedagogy:**

This method of ELT mostly influenced learning language among students. regional system to teach English in College of rural area commonly used Translation method and rote learning Because student just want to pass out English subject and it's gate more difficult to English teacher to make rural students to be a English speaker.

Enhancing English proficiency of rural areas students:

In the education department take few steps to change the scenario of English proficiency among the rural students so it will be possible. they have to introduce device different ways of developing English proficiency among rural students few additional steps can help to improve scenario of English language in rural area.

1. Languages skills reading, writing, speaking and listening should be focused equally. Only English teacher should not pay the attention to the development of English communication of college or school students but other subject teachers should teach their subject in English accepting Hindi and Marathi.
2. Teacher should develop learning resources as per the need and background of rural students because there are lace of facilities available to learn English language in rural area.
3. ICT use become interesting and innovative method of teaching so education system should provide this facility to the school and colleges so it will develop students interest towards the education and it will going to develop their confidence to learn English language.
4. Students background have to considered for teaching strategies while teaching in classroom.
5. Classroom size should be reduce from 120 to 50 So teacher will able to pay attention on every

child so it will affect To development of students.

Conclusion.

Institute effort to make rural students proficiency in English and increase the employability in global market since English is there third language. effective implementation curriculum most important way faculty development programs FDP by providing facilities and environment availability will going to help to students development towards the proficiency in English language .

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